

Chemical characterisation of galena by ICP-AES/AAS after decomposition with various fluxes and acid leaching of the samples

Roopa Bose*, V. S. Keshavan and Smeer Durani

Chemistry Laboratory, Southern Region, Atomic Minerals Directorate for Exploration and Research,
Department of Atomic Energy, Nagarabhavi, Bangalore-560 072, India

E-mail : roopabenaras@yahoo.co.in

Abstract : Galena is the most widely distributed of the sulphide minerals and the most important of the lead minerals. Literature survey indicates lack of decomposition procedure yielding a single solution for estimation of major and minor constituents of this highly insoluble lead mineral. An attempt has been made to attain the same by using mixed phosphate fluxes and the results compared with the decomposition of the samples with sodium peroxide. The methods have been optimised with respect to most suitable leaching agent, time of leaching, temperature required etc. An acid leaching procedure for the estimation of the geochemically significant traces in the sulphide matrix has also been standardised yielding minimum dissolution of lead and quantitative leaching of the traces. Standard lead concentrate sample, CPB-1, was simultaneously analysed to validate the procedure. The accuracy of the proposed method has also been established by determination of some of the elements by two analytical techniques ICP-AES and flame AAS. The reproducibility studies carried out with ($n = 5$) show the RSD of 2 to 6%.

Keywords : Galena, mixed phosphate flux, ICP-AES, AAS.

Introduction

Galena is of importance both as a principal mineral of lead and for use of lead sulphide for optoelectronics. Metal sulphides in general ZnS, HgS, CdS and PbS are common semiconductors that have received extensive attention in the field of solid state chemistry and solar energy research. As a part of geochemical study of such occurrences, major, minor and certain geochemically significant trace elemental analysis have been carried out in galena samples collected from neoproterozoic alkali pink syenite of Rasimalai area, emplaced within Dharmapuri shear zone in the northern part of Tamilnadu, about 20 km NE of Alangayam in Vellore district, occurring as specks, granular aggregates, chunks and disseminations. Lead sulphide (principal composition of galena) with solubility product¹ of $10^{-28.3}$ is one of the most insoluble lead minerals. Few of the suggested decomposition methods for galena samples are lithium metaborate-dilute mineral acid method² and sodium peroxide fusion^{3,4}. A detailed study of dissolution kinetics of galena in nitric acid solution with hydrogen peroxide⁵, in binary solutions of HCl/FeCl₃ and HCl/H₂O₂⁶, in acetic acid solution with hydro-

gen peroxide⁷, and dissolution of lead from powdered galena ore using hypochlorous acid in excess chloride⁸, leaching of PbS with HNO₃⁹ are well documented. Solid studies for structural determination, chemical composition, electronic structure and determination of surface chemical reactivity have also been studied in detail¹⁰. As the literature survey depicts a lack of any simple, rapid, step-wise procedure for chemical analysis of galena for the estimation of traces like Cu, Cd, Zn, Sb, Bi and As and major/minor elements like Pb, Fe, Al, Si, S, Mg, Mn and Ti, therefore the most suitable fusion technique and a mineral acid leaching procedure have been optimized for chemical characterisation of the galena samples with respect to the mentioned elements. Validation of the methods suggested was done by analysis of a reference standard, lead concentrate CPB-1. Two analytical techniques were used for the same element determination wherever possible to further validate the recovery % as well as to monitor the spectral and the matrix effects, if any, during the course of instrumental determinations. The reproducibility studies carried out with ($n = 5$) show the RSD of 2 to 6%.

Experimental

Reagents : All reagents and chemicals used were either of analytical or GR grade and double distilled water was used throughout the experiments.

Instrument : A Jobin Yvon model 2000(2) ICP-AES sequential spectrometer from Jobin Yvon, Horiba, France Make was used. Detection limits, L/B ratios and BEC of the elements analysed are tabulated in Table 1. The instrumental parameters are the same as already documented¹¹. The Flame AAS used was of GBC Australia, Avanta-P model. It was used for the determination of Pb (217.0 nm), Fe (371 nm), Zn (213.90 nm), Cu (324.70 nm) and Cd (288.80 nm) using air-acetylene flame adopting standard operating parameters which included deuterium lamp background correction at the appropriate wavelengths .

Preparation of standards : A stock solution of 1000 µg/ml each was prepared from the spectrographically pure (> 99.99%) oxides/salts of Pb, S, Fe, Si, Al, Ca, Mg, Mn, P, Zn, Sb, Cu, Bi and Cd employing suitable acid digestion/dissolution procedures. Working standard solution for instrumental calibration was prepared by serial dilution of stock standard solution. Individual and batches of reference standard solutions prepared were (a) Pb, Si : 5–50 µg ml⁻¹; (b) S : 5–50 µg ml⁻¹; (c) Fe, Al, Ca, Mg,

Mn : 0.5–10 µg ml⁻¹; (d) Zn, Sb, Al, As, Bi : 0.5–4 µg ml⁻¹. All standards were made in 5% HCl.

Sample decomposition procedure : Three sample decomposition/dissolution procedures were used for the dissolution of galena samples :

(A) *Mixed phosphate fusion* : 0.25 g of the sample was weighed in a 30 ml capacity Pt crucible and evaporated to dryness on a water bath with 5 ml of concentrated hydrofluoric acid and 3 ml of concentrated nitric acid. 2 g of 1 : 1 mixture of monobasic sodium phosphate (NaH₂PO₄) and dibasic sodium phosphate (Na₂HPO₄) was weighed and added to the crucible with the treated sample. It was then melted over a burner and the temperature increased to red hot condition. The crucible was covered with a lid and the heating continued for fifteen minutes. Then the clear glassy melt thus obtained was swirled along the walls of the crucible while cooling. A thin film of the melt was formed around the crucible walls which facilitate the leaching of the melt. After cooling, the crucible and its contents were transferred into a 500 ml beaker containing 3 ml of concentrated nitric acid and 1 ml of H₂O₂ and kept on water bath for a period of 10 min to obtain a clear solution. It was then diluted to 100 ml. The solution thus obtained was aspirated into ICP-AES for estimation of trace elements like Bi, As, Sb and into AAS

Table 1. Spectral lines used for emission measurement of Pb, Ti, Fe, Al, Mn, Si, Ca, Mg, P, Si, S, Bi, Sb and As, BG correction points, BEC, L/B and D.L. values

Element	Wavelength (nm)	Background correction		Concentration (µg/ml)	BEC ^a (µg/ml)	L/B	D.L. ^b (µg/L)
		Left (nm)	Right (nm)				
Pb	216.999	0.019	0.018	10	0.49	21	0.015
Ti	334.941	0.02	0.015	20	0.45	46	0.014
Fe	238.204	0.019	0.017	25	0.42	60	0.013
Al	396.152	0.024	0.019	25	0.42	60	0.013
Mn	257.610	0.022	0.017	5	0.15	114	0.004
Ca	422.673	0.018	0.018	10	0.15	33	0.004
Mg	285.213	0.022	0.020	10	0.40	24	0.012
P	214.914	0.019	0.019	5	0.90	5.1	0.027
Si	251.661	0.018	0.018	30	1.04	30	0.031
S	180.670	0.019	0.018	50	2.49	41	0.074
Bi	223.061	0.018	0.017	25	0.37	28	0.011
Sb	217.581	0.018	0.017	10	0.46	23	0.014
As	193.695	0.020	0.009	2	0.30	8	0.009

^aBEC is calculated from : Concentration (µg/ml) $I_b/(I_p - I_b)$, where I_p and I_b represents peak counts and background counts respectively.

^bD.L. is calculated based on three times the standard deviation of the blank at 1% RSD (D.L. = BEC × 0.03).

for the estimation of Cu and Cd. 1 ml of the stock solution was diluted to 100 ml for estimation of Pb, Fe and S by ICP-AES repeating Pb and Fe by AAS. The other elements Al, Ca, Mg, Mn and Ti were determined by ICP-AES and Zn by AAS after a further dilution of the stock (3 to 50 ml).

(B) *Sodium peroxide fusion* : 0.5 g (-200 mesh) galena sample was weighed in a 60 ml nickel crucible with 5 g of sodium peroxide flux, in duplicate, and mixed thoroughly. The covered crucible with the fusion flux mixture was initially subjected to a low flame which was gradually increased to get a clear melt. The melt was occasionally swirled until a clear transparent melt was obtained. The content of the cooled crucible was transferred to a 600 ml beaker with distilled water followed by 1 : 1 HCl. The contents were boiled to obtain a clear solution. Finally the volume maintained was 100 ml, maintaining 10% (v/v) acidity in HCl after neutralization. 1 ml of this solution was diluted to 100 ml for the estimation of Pb, S, Fe and Al by ICP-AES. 3 ml of aliquot from the stock was diluted to 50 ml for the estimation of Zn, Si, Ti, Ca, Mg, Mn and P by ICP-AES. Pb, Zn and Fe were also estimated by AAS. Cd and Cu were estimated in the stock solution by flame AAS.

The fused sample melt in duplicate was transferred to a 600 ml beaker with the help of distilled water followed by 1 : 1 HNO₃. The solution was boiled to obtain a clear melt with the addition of few drops of H₂O₂. After neutralization, the solution was made up to a final volume of 250 ml maintaining 5% (v/v) acidity in HNO₃. Two ml of the stock solution was diluted to 100 ml for the estimation of the major elements Pb, Al, Fe and S. Zn, Si, Ti, Ca, Mg, Mn and P were estimated after the dilution of 5 ml of the master solution to 50 ml. Cu and Cd were estimated in the stock solution by aspiration into flame AAS. Zn, Pb and Fe contents were also estimated by flame AAS in the diluted solution. Matrix matching standards were used for the estimation of Cu and Cd by flame AAS to overcome any matrix effect due to high salt concentration of the stock solution.

(C) *Acid leaching* : Accurately weighed 0.5 g of finely powdered rock material in a platinum dish, moistened with water, added 5 ml of HF and evaporated to dryness. Added 10 ml of HF to the dried residue and again evapo-

rated to dryness. The dried sample was then moistened with 10 ml 0.17 N HNO₃ (0.5%) and kept on water bath for a short while before transferring the same into a 600 ml beaker with 0.5% HNO₃ such that the volume maintained was approximately 100 ml. A few drops of sulphurous acid were added to the contents of the beaker prior to boiling for five minutes on the burner to obtain a clear separation of the precipitate and the filtrate. The slightly warm solution was filtered using Whatman 542 filter paper and ashless powder. A final volume of 25 ml was maintained of the filtrate for the estimation of traces like Bi, Sb, As by ICP-AES and Zn (after dilution) Cd and Cu by flame-AAS.

Results and discussion

Evaluation of the sample decomposition procedures :

The sample was initially treated with HF/HNO₃ to remove traces of silica prior to fusion with a 1 : 1 mixture of sodium dihydrogen and di sodium hydrogen orthophosphate as it may remain unattacked by the phosphate flux during fusion. A clear glassy melt was obtained within 10 to 15 min which when leached in water as reported in literature for other mineral fractions¹²⁻¹⁶ took several hours to detach from the walls of the Pt crucible. Traces of white residue were left at the bottom of the beaker while leaching with water only. This was probably due to the formation of a small fraction of insoluble lead phosphate due to traces of orthophosphate left behind along with the polyphosphates in the molten flux¹⁷. The other insoluble species likely to be formed at pH 7 and in presence of >10 mg/ml lead concentration is hydroxypyromorphite, Pb₅(PO₄)₃OH¹⁸ according to the equation $5\text{Pb}^{2+} + 3\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4^- + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{Pb}_5(\text{PO}_4)_3\text{OH} + 7\text{H}^+$. Therefore the leaching was done in presence of 3 ml of HNO₃ and 1 ml of H₂O₂ (to accelerate the reaction) on water bath, which solubilised all the insoluble Pb species as Pb(NO₃)₂ within 10 min and a clear solution was obtained thereafter. Major, minor and trace element analysis of Pb, S, Fe, Al, Ca, Mg, Mn, Ti, Bi, Cd, Cu, Sb and As were done using ICP-AES and AAS in the sample solution after appropriate dilutions. The results have been tabulated in Table 2. Sulphur could not be recovered quantitatively and the cause is being studied.

Table 2. A comparative study of different decomposition techniques of galena samples for the estimation of Pb, S, Fe, Zn, SiO₂, Al₂O₃, MgO, MnO, P₂O₅, TiO₂, Bi, Sb, As, Cd and Cu-determination using ICP-AES/AAS (values averaged for reporting)

Element	Lead concentrate (%) ^a					Galena 1 (values in (%))				Galena 2 (values in (%))			
	Na ₂ O ₂ fusion		Reported (%)	Phosphate fusion	Acid leach	Na ₂ O ₂ fusion		Phosphate fusion	Acid leach	Na ₂ O ₂ fusion		Phosphate fusion	Acid leach
	1 ^b	2 ^c				1	2			1	2		
Pb	63.28	62.99	64.74	63.34	6.84	69.15	67.99	69.22	5.55	43.0	42.5	42.0	2.50
S	16.60	14.22	17.8	10.66	-	18.16	16.45	12.20	-	8.11	8.01	5.01	-
Fe	7.98	7.12	8.43	8.12	7.99	0.35 ^e	0.34	0.35	0.32	18.43 ^d	18.01 ^d	18.02 ^d	18.22 ^d
Zn	4.14	3.33	4.42	4.02	3.99	<0.01	<0.01	-	-	-	-	-	-
SiO ₂	0.55	0.34	0.74	-	-	6.52	6.58	-	-	15.6	15.16	-	-
Al ₂ O ₃	0.22	0.20	0.28	0.22	0.27	0.96	0.88	0.82	0.90	6.60	6.1	5.9	6.2
MgO	-	-	-	-	-	0.05	0.04	0.05	0.05	1.3	1.0	1.1	1.1
MnO	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.29	0.22	0.21	0.22
P ₂ O ₅	-	-	-	-	-	1.15	1.13	-	-	1.11	1.13	-	-
TiO ₂	-	-	-	-	-	0.03	0.03	0.03	-	0.22	0.20	-	-
Bi	-	-	0.023	-	0.02	-	-	0.40	0.42	0.30	0.28	0.25	-
Sb	-	-	0.360	-	0.35	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
As	-	-	0.056	-	0.05	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Cd	-	-	0.014	-	0.01	-	-	0.06	0.06	<0.01	<0.01	-	-
Cu	-	-	0.254	-	0.24	-	-	0.1	0.1	0.08	0.06	-	0.07

^aLead concentrate CPB-1,^bLeached with 10% HCl,^cLeached with 10% HNO₃+ 2% H₂O₂,^dFe as Fe₂O₃.

In the course of dissolution of complex sulphide mineral by fusion with the strongly oxidizing Na₂O₂, followed by leaching with hydrochloric acid to obtain a clear solution for major and minor elemental analysis, the strongly oxidizing flux oxidized lead sulphide to insoluble lead sulphate. This in presence of 1 : 1 HCl, precipitated out initially as lead chloride crystals prior to dissolution in excess of conc. HCl to give yellow coloured solution of chloroplumbates containing different species of lead like PbCl₄²⁻, PbCl₃⁻ etc. Thus this fusion procedure resulted into the complete dissolution of the sample and all the major and minor elements along with a few trace elements (Pb, Fe, Al, S, Ca, Mg, Mn, P, Si and Zn, Cu and Cd) of galena samples were determined as indicated in Table 2.

Leaching with nitric acid was done in the presence of the oxidant, hydrogen peroxide to obtain a clear solution rapidly with minimum consumption of acid. The most probable reason for the reaction to be accelerated was *in situ* regeneration of the acid. Moreover hydrogen perox-

ide is an environmentally safe reagent as apart from water no other products generated during the dissolution of sulphide minerals⁵. A comparative data of both the above mentioned methods have been tabulated in Table 2.

During the galena dissolution in nitric acid solution the parameters pertaining to the concentration required of HNO₃ for minimum leaching of lead and quantitative recovery of traces as well as other conditions of digestion like temperature and time for partial leaching have been optimized using the standard lead concentrate as depicted in Fig. 1. It was observed that when lead sulphide was treated with HNO₃ alone varying in molarity from 0.5 N to 5.1 N, minimum leaching of lead occurred with the HNO₃ concentration ranging from 0.1 N to 0.2 N. The concentration of HNO₃ maintained during course of this study was 0.17 N (0.5%). This concentration of acid leached a small amount of lead due to rapid reagent depletion caused by oxidation of sulphides to elemental sulphur and then sulphate¹⁹. The elemental sulphur produced was oxidized to bisulphate ion which combined with lead

Fig. 1. Dissolution of Pb with varying concentration of HNO₃.

and caused its precipitation²⁰. $S^0 + 2NO_3^- + H^+ \rightarrow 2NO(g) + HSO_4^-$; $Pb^{2+} + HSO_4^- \rightarrow H^+ + PbSO_4(s)$. There was an increase of lead dissolution with increase in acid concentration levelling off at approximately 40% after 15 min of digestion on boiling water bath probably due to passivation by increased sulphate formation. But with water bath digestion followed by boiling on burner for 10 min, the dissolution of lead was more than 60% at a higher concentration of acid. As boiling with a few drops of sulphurous acid was essential to obtain a clear separation between the two phases, the minimum acid molarity of 0.17 N was maintained. Sulphurous acid acted as a coagulant to collect together the dispersed precipitate of lead sulphate and helped in the formation of coarser and easily filterable precipitate only. It is not acting as a reducing agent as oxidation of sulphurous acid generally takes place in presence of oxidizing catalysts like oxides of Mn, ferric and cupric salts or free oxygen in presence of dissolved salt²¹. The amount of nitric acid added is utilised in formation of lead sulphate, lead sulphide being the major matrix. The filtrate was made up to a final volume of 25 ml. Thus a dilution factor of fifty could be maintained which was very suitable for the determination of trace elements. It was also observed that the trace elements did not suffer any noticeable spectral overlap at the wavelengths considered nor there was any significant change in the plasma conditions of ICP-AES caused due to the dissolved lead in the filtrate. The recovery % of traces by AAS did not suffer any matrix effect due to the residual lead in the final solution. The values obtained of the analysis of one standard sample, a lead concentrate CPB-1, one pure galena sample and an impure galena

sample with less sulphur content and more iron content, received from Rasimalai area, Tamilnadu by the three different optimised methodologies, have been summarized in Table 2.

The lithium metaborate – dilute mineral acid method could not be applied as for overcoming the wetting properties of the flux the fusion had to be carried out in Au alloyed Pt crucible which could be corroded due to the presence of high sulphur content of the sample.

Conclusion

Due to the lack of a systematic scheme of chemical analysis of trace elements along with major and minor elements in pure galena samples, an attempt has been made for developing a simple method for trace element analysis in galena by partial dissolution of the matrix in nitric acid. As this procedure does not involve fusion fluxes therefore a maximum of 50 times dilution factor could be maintained which facilitated the detection of traces like Bi, Sb, As, Cu, Cd and Zn by ICP-AES, since high salt content of the fused melts restricts nebulisation of the stock into the plasma/flame. Also a rapid and convenient fusion technique using a mixture of monobasic and dibasic sodium phosphate (1 : 1) flux for complete dissolution of the sample for the estimation of major, minor and few of the trace elements has been successfully attempted. The results obtained have been compared with those obtained by dissolution of the sample using sodium peroxide flux followed by dissolution of the melt in HCl/HNO₃-H₂O₂ as tabulated in Table 2. The phosphate flux suggested is more easy to handle, non-corrosive and the sample – flux mixture treated in Pt crucible,

hence free from Ni contamination. The sample : flux ratio is 1 : 8 when compared to sodium peroxide fusion in which the minimum sample : flux ratio to be maintained is 1 : 10. Therefore the sample solution is easier to aspirate into the plasma for ICP-AES determinations without any probability of nebulizer blockage or difficulty in sustaining the plasma. Leaching of the phosphate melt does not involve any vigorous reactions and is not exothermic and therefore is more simple to handle without loss in sample due to spurting etc. during dissolution as in the case of sodium peroxide melt. Thus the fusion procedure is user and environment friendly. Some of the documented methods of opening of lead samples involving lead removal followed by gravimetric or photometric estimation^{22,23} pertains to estimation of lead in silicate matrix and involves repeated acid treatment with HF/HNO₃/HCl followed by solvent extraction using dithizone/diethyldithiocarbamate/TOPO in MIBK etc. All these procedures involve numerous acid treatment steps and tedious solvent extraction procedures. The instrumental determination of the elements is restricted to AAS which in turn restricts the number of traces which can be determined. Hence the present procedures studied for chemical characterisation of galena involving the determination of the elements both by flame AAS and ICP-AES is rapid, easy, economical and includes a wider spectrum of trace elements for analysis.

Validity and the accuracy of the proposed method was established by analysing standard lead concentrate (CPB-1) simultaneously, and the results obtained are in close agreement with the reported values confirming the accuracy of the proposed method. The validity of the method was also confirmed by comparison of the values obtained of the samples including the two natural samples from Rasimalai area, Vellore District, Tamilnadu, by two different decomposition techniques and were found to be in good agreement with each other. The reproducibility is characterized by the RSD of the present procedure as a whole (n = 5) is about 1-6% which characterizes the reproducibility of the method.

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